

LINE SET TRIPLE CONNECTED DOMINATION NUMBER OF GRAPH

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ABSTRACT : The concept of triple connected graphs with real life application was introduced by Paul raj Joseph et.al.by considering the existence of a path containing any three vertices of a graph G.Mahadevan et.al. introduced the concept of triple connected domination number of a graph . A subset S of V of a nontrivial connected graph G is said to be triple connected dominating set, if S is a dominating set and the induced subgraph $\langle S \rangle$ is triple connected.A subset F of the edge set E(G) of a graph G is called line set dominating if for each subset $S \subseteq E - F$, there exists an edge $ee \in L$ such that the subgraph $\langle S \cup \{e\} \rangle$ induced by $S \cup \{e\}$ is connected.In this paper, we introduce new domination parameter line set triple connected domination number of a graph as follows,A subset L of the edge set E(G) of a nontrivial connected graph G is said to be a line set triple connected dominating set, if L is a line set dominating set and the induced sub graph $\langle L \rangle$ is triple connected. The maximum cardinality taken over all line set triple connected dominating sets is called the line set triple connected domination number and is denoted by $v'_{ltc}(G)$. We determine this number for some standard graphs and obtain bounds for general graph.Its relationships with other domination parameters were found.

Keywords : Dominating set, Triple connected graph, Triple connected domination number of graph, Line set triple connected domination number of graph.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Let $G = (V, E)$ be a finite simple undirected graph of order n and size m. where V denote its vertex set and E its edge set. Unless otherwise stated, the graph G has p vertices and q edges. The degree of an edge $e = uv$ of G is defined by $deg(e) = deg(u) + deg(v) - 2$. The maximum and minimum degree among the edge of graph G is denote by $\Delta'(G)$ & $\lambda'(G)$. (the degree of an edge is the number of edges adjacent to it.) A Graph G is said to be connected if any two vertices are joined by a path in G; otherwise the graph is disconnected.

A maximal connected sub graph of a graph G is called a component of G. The number of components of a graph G is denoted by $\omega(G)$. A vertex v of a connected graph G is a cut vertex if $G - v$ is disconnected. An edge e of a connected graph G is a cut edge if $G - e$ is disconnected. A connected graph with at least one cut edge is called a separable graph.

The connectivity $\kappa(G)$ of a graph G is the minimum number of points whose removal results in a disconnected or trivial graph. The line connectivity $\kappa'(G)$ of G is the minimum number of lines whose removal results in a disconnected or trivial graph.

A Domination is an active subject in graph theory. Let $G=(V,E)$ be a graph. A set $D \subseteq V(G)$ of vertices in a graph $G =(V,E)$ is a dominating set. if every vertex in $V-D$ is adjacent to some vertex in D. The domination number $\gamma(G)$ of G is the minimum cardinality of dominating set in G.

A dominating set D is called a minimal dominating set, if no proper subset of D is a dominating set.

Let $G=(V,E)$ be a graph . A set $F \subseteq E$ is an edge dominating set of G , if and only if every edge in $E - F$ is adjacent to some edge in F . The edge domination number $\gamma'(G)$ of G is the minimum of cardinalities of all edge dominating sets of G .(Hedetniemi and Laskar).

Let G be a graph. A set $D \subseteq V(G)$ is a point set dominating set (PSD-set) of G , if for each set $S \subseteq V-D$, there exists a vertex u in D such that the sub graph $\langle S \cup \{e\} \rangle$ induced by $S \cup \{e\}$ is connected. The point set domination number (PSD-number) $\gamma'_p(G)$ of G is the minimum cardinalities of all PSD-Set of G .

I.H.Nagaraja Rao & B.Vijayalakmi introduced the concept of Line set domination set and derived results parallel to those of E.Sampathkumar and L.Pushpalatha.

Let G be a graph. A set $F \subseteq E$ is a line set dominating set (LSD-set) of G , if for each set $L \subseteq E-F$, there exists an edge e in F such that the sub graph $\langle L \cup \{e\} \rangle$ induced by $L \cup \{e\}$ is connected. The line set domination number (LSD-number) $v'_{lsc}(G)$ of G is the minimum cardinalities of all LSD-Set of G .

A line graph $L(G)$ is the graph whose vertices corresponds to the edges of G and two vertices in $L(G)$ are adjacent if and only if the corresponding edges in G are adjacent ($V(L(G))=q$). For any edge e , let $N'(e) = \{e \in F : e \text{ and } f \text{ have a vertex in common}\}$ and $N'[e] = N'(e) \cup \{x\}$, For a set $F \subseteq E(G)$, Let $N'(F) = \cup N'(e)$.

$$I_v(L) = \{v \in V : v \text{ is incident with some edge in } L\} \text{ where } L \text{ is a line set dominating set in } G.$$

A graph G is said to be triple connected if any three vertices lie on a path in G .

A subset S of V of a nontrivial connected graph G is said to be triple connected dominating set, if S is a dominating set and the induced sub graph $\langle S \rangle$ is triple connected.

In this paper , we use this idea to develop the concept of line set triple connected dominating set and line set triple connected domination number of a graph.

2 RESULTS

Definition 2.1 A subset L of the edge set $E(G)$ of a nontrivial connected graph G is said to be a line set triple connected dominating set, if L is a line set dominating set and the induced sub graph $\langle L \rangle$ is triple connected. The minimum cardinality taken over all line set triple connected dominating sets is called the line set triple connected domination number and is denoted by $v'_{ltc}(G)$.

Example 2.1 For the graph G_1 in figure 2.1, $L = \{e_1, e_5, e_6\}$ forms a $v'_{ltc}(G)$. Hence $v'_{ltc}(G) = 3$.

Figure 2.1

Observation 2.1 Every line set triple connected dominating set is edge dominating set but not conversely.

Observation 2.2 For any connected graph G , $v'_l(G) \leq v'_{ltc}(G)$ and for the cycle C_5 the bounds are sharp.

Exact value for some standard graphs:

Observation 2.3 For any complete graph K_p of order $n \geq 4$, $v'_{ltc}(K_n) = n - 1$.

Observation 2.4 For any path P_n of order $n \geq 5$, $v'_{ltc}(P_n) = n - 2$.

Observation 2.5 For any path C_n of order $n \geq 5$, then $v'_{ltc}(C_n) = n - 2$.

Observation 2.6 For any complete bi-partite graph $K_{n,m}$ of order $n \geq 4$, then

$$v'_{ltc}(K_{m,n}) = \begin{cases} m + 1 & \text{for } m = n \\ n & \text{for } m < n \end{cases}$$

Observation 2.7 For any wheel graph W_n of order $n \geq 4$, then $v'_{ltc}(W_n) = n - 1$.

Observation 2.8 If every non end edges of a (p,q) tree T is adjacent to at least one end edge, then $v'_{ltc}(T) = 3$.

In the next result, Line set triple connected dominating set in Line graph $L(G)$

Observation 2.9 For any path P_n for any positive $n \geq 5$ vertices. $v'_{ltc}(L(G)) = n - 2$.

Observation 2.10 For any cycle C_n for any positive $n \geq 5$ vertices. $v'_{ltc}(L(G)) = n - 2$.

Observation 2.11 For any star $K_{1,n}$ with $n \geq 2$. $v'_{ltc}(L(K_{1,n})) = v'_{ltc}(K_{n-1}(G))$.

Exact value for some special graphs:

1.The Moser spindle (also called the Moser’s spindle or Moser graph) is an undirected graph, named after mathematicians Leo Moser and his brother William, with seven vertices and eleven edges gives in Figure 2.2 .

Figure 2.2

For the Moser spindle graph $G, v'_{ltc}(G) = 6$.

2.The Wagner graph is a 3-regular graph with 8 vertices and 16 edges gives in Figure 2.3

VERTEX = 8, EDGE = 16

Figure 2.3

For the Wanger graph $G, v'_{ltc}(G) = 8$.

Theorem 2.1 For any connected graph G with $n \geq 4$, we have $3 \leq v'_{ltc}(G) \leq q - 1$ and the bounds are sharp.

Proof: The lower and upper bounds trivially follows from Definition 2.1 For C_4 the lower bound is attained and for P_n , the upper bound is attained.

Observation 2.12 Let G be a connected graph and H be a spanning sub graph of G . If H has a line set triple connected dominating set, then $v'_{ltc}(G) \leq v'_{ltc}(H)$ and the bound sharp. C_4

Example 2.2 For the graph G in figure 2.4 $F = \{e_1, e_4, e_{10}\}$ is a line set triple connected domination set and so $v'_{ltc}(G) = 3$. For the spanning sub graph H of G . $S(G) = \{e_6, e_7, e_9\}$ is a line set triple connected domination set and so $v'_{ltc}(G) = 3$.

Figure 2.4

Theorem 2.2 For any connected graph G with $n \geq 4$, and $\Delta'(G) = q - 2$, Then $v'_{ltc}(G) = 3$. (where $\Delta'(G)$ is maximum degree of edge, $deg(e) = deg(u) + deg(v) - 2$).

Proof:

Let G be a connected graph with (p, q) and $\Delta'(G) = q - 2$ and let $e = uv$ be an edge of maximum degree $\Delta'(G) = q - 2$. Let $e_1, e_2, e_3, \dots, e_{q-2}$ be an edges which are adjacent to e and let e_{q-1} be the edge which is not adjacent to e . since G is connected, e_{q-1} is adjacent to an edge e_i for some i then $F = \{e, e_i, e_j\}$, for some $i \neq j$ is a line set triple connected dominating set of G . Hence $v'_{ltc}(G) = 3$.

Theorem 2.3 For any connected graph G with $n \geq 4$, and $\Delta'(G) = q - 3$, Then $v'_{ltc}(G) = 3$.

Proof:

Let G be a connected graph with $n \geq 4$, and $\Delta'(G) = q - 3$, and let $e = uv$ be an edge of maximum degree $\Delta'(G) = q - 3$. Suppose $N(e) = \{e_1, e_2, e_3, \dots, e_{q-3}\}$ and $E - N(e) = \{e_{q-1}, e_{q-2}\}$. If e_{q-1}, e_{q-2} are not adjacent in G , then since G is connected, there are edges e_i and e_j for some $i, j, 1 \leq i, j \leq q - 3$ which are adjacent to e_{q-2} and e_{q-1} . If $i = j$, then $\{e, e_i, e_{q-1}\}$ is a line set triple connected dominating set of G , $i \neq j$ then $\{e_i, e, e_j\}$ is a triple connected dominating set of G . If e_{q-1}, e_{q-2} are adjacent in G , then there is a edge e_j , for some $j, 1 \leq j \leq n - 3$, which is adjacent to e_{q-1} or to both. In this case, $\{e, e_i, e_{q-1}\}$ or $\{e, e_i, e_{q-2}\}$ is a line set triple connected dominating set of G . Hence $v'_{ltc}(G) = 3$.

Theorem 2.4 Let G be a connected graph with $n \geq 5$, If $v'_{ltc}(G) = q - 2$, then $\kappa(G) = 1$ or 2 , $\Delta'(G) = 2$ and $diam(G) = n - 1$ or $n/2$.

$$[Diam(G) = \left\{ \max_{u,v \in V(G)} d(u, v) \right\} \text{ for } u \in I_v(L), v \notin I_v(L), \text{ where } L \text{ is line set triple connected dominating set}]$$

Proof:

Let G be a connected graph with $n \geq 5$, and $v'_{ltc}(G) = q-2$, since $v'_{ltc}(G) = q-2$, $G \cong P_n, C_n$. we known that for $P_n, \kappa'(G) = 1, \Delta'(G) = 2$ and $diam(G) = n-1$. For $C_n, \kappa'(G) = 2, \Delta'(G) = 2$ and $diam(G) = n/2$.

Nordhaus - Gaddum Type result:

Theorem 2.5 Let G be a graph such that G and \overline{G} have no isolates of order $n \geq 5$, then

$$(i)v'_{ltc}(G) + v'_{ltc}(\overline{G}) \leq 2(q-2).$$

$$(ii)v'_{ltc}(G) \cdot v'_{ltc}(\overline{G}) \leq (q-2)^2 \text{ and the bounds are sharp.}$$

Proof:

The bounds directly follows from Theorem 2.1. For cycle $C_5, v'_{ltc}(G) + v'_{ltc}(\overline{G}) \leq 2(q-2)$ and $v'_{ltc}(G) \cdot v'_{ltc}(\overline{G}) \leq (q-2)^2$.

Line set triple connected domination number and other parameters.

Theorem 2.6 For any connected graph G with $n \geq 4, v'_{ltc}(G) + \kappa'(G) \leq 2q-3$ and the bounds sharp if and only if $G \cong C_4, K_{1,3}, K_{2,2}$.

Proof:

Let G be a connected graph with $n \geq 4$ we known that $\kappa'(G) \leq q-2$ and by the theorem 2.1, $v'_{ltc}(G) \leq q-1$. Hence $v'_{ltc}(G) + \kappa'(G) \leq q-1 + q-2 \Rightarrow v'_{ltc}(G) + \kappa'(G) \leq 2q-3$. Since G is isomorphic to C_4 . Thus $v'_{ltc}(G) + \kappa'(G) \leq 2q-3$. Conversely, let $v'_{ltc}(G) + \kappa'(G) \leq 2q-3$. This is possible only if $v'_{ltc}(G) \leq q-1$ and $\kappa'(G) \leq q-2$. But $\kappa'(G) \leq q-2$, and so G is isomorphic to $K_{1,3} + e$, for which $v'_{ltc}(G) = 3 = q-1$ so that $n = 4$. Hence $G \cong C_4$.

Theorem 2.7 For any connected graph G with $n \geq 4, v'_{ltc}(G) + \Delta'(G) \leq 2q-3$ and the bounds sharp if and only if G is isomorphic to $K_4 - e, K_{1,3} + e, C_3(2P_2)$.

Proof:

Let G be a connected graph with $n \geq 4$ we known that $\Delta'(G) \leq q-1$ and $v'_{ltc}(G) \leq q-2$. Hence $v'_{ltc}(G) + \Delta'(G) \leq q-2 + q-1 \leq 2q-3$. Let G is isomorphic to $K_4 - e, K_{1,3} + e, C_3(2P_2)$, then clearly $v'_{ltc}(G) + \Delta'(G) \leq 2q-3$. Conversely, let $v'_{ltc}(G) + \Delta'(G) \leq 2q-3$. This is possible only if $v'_{ltc}(G) \leq q-2$ and $\Delta'(G) \leq q-1$. We have G is isomorphic to $K_4 - e, K_{1,3} + e, C_3(2P_2)$.

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References :

- [1]. Alavi. Y, and J.E. Williamson, (1975), *Panconnected Graphs, Studio Scientianem Mathematicarum Hungarica, 10, 19 - 22.*
- [2]. E. Sampathkumar and L. Pushpalatha, *Point set domination number of a graph, Indian J. Pure appl. Math. 24 (1993).*
- [3]. Gary Chartrand, and Ping Zhang, (2006), *Introduction to Graph Theory, Tata McGraw-Hill Edition.*
- [4]. Haynes T.W., Hedetniemi S.T. and Slater P.J., (1998), *Fundamentals of domination in graphs, New York, Marcel Dekker, Inc.*

- [5].Haynes T.W.,Hedetniemi S.T. and Slater P.J.,(1999), *Domination in Graph Advanced Topics*.
- [6].I.H.Nagaraja Rao and B.VijayaLakshmi, *Line set domination Number of a Graph Indian J. pure appl. Math.30(7):709 - 713 (1999)*.
- [7].J.A.Bondy, and U.S.R.Murty,(2008), *Graph Theory, Springer*.
- [8]. Mahadevan G.Selvam A.,Paulraj Joseph J., and Subramanian T.(2012): *Triple connected domination number of a graph, International J.Math.Combin. Vol,3 93- 104*.
- [9].S.Arumugam and S.Velammal *Edge dominating in graphs Taiwanese J. of Mathematics (1998)*.
- [10].E.Sampathkumar and L.Pushpalatha, *Point set domination number of a graph,Indian J.Pure appl.Math.24 (1993)*.